

UX and Product Lifecycle										Q = QUESTION
Experience	Q20	Q21	Q22	Techniques	Tools	Practices	Challenges	Q27	P = PARTICIPANT	
P1	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	3	1	5	Usability testing, Benchmarking, Interviews, Wireframing, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture	Figma, Miro	Does not adopt	Validating the game with the end user, Extracting user information, Understanding the target audience, Hiring UX professionals	5	
P2	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	5	5	5	Cannot answer	Figma, Miro, Google Analytics	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, data analysis and telemetry.	Extract user information	5	
P3	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	4	4	2	User flow map, Teste de usabilidade, GDD (Game Design Document) ou GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture	Figma	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development	Game validation with the end user, Extract user information, Understand the target audience	4	
P4	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	4	1	1	High-fidelity prototype, Wireframe, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Google Analytics, FireBase	Iterations with user feedback, data analysis and telemetry, responsive design for different devices.	Game validation with the end user	5	
P5	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	5	4	4	User flow map, Teste de usabilidade, Benchmarking, Survey, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Figma, Miro, Google Analytics, FireBase, Canva	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, User-centered development	Game validation with the end user, Extracting user information, Applications of UX techniques	5	
P6	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	3	1	1	Do not adopt, Cannot answer	Does not use	User-centered development	Lack of UX knowledge	4	
P7	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	3	1	1	Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Cognitive ergonomics	Miro, Google Analytics, FireBase	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, data analysis and telemetry, responsive design for different devices.	Has no challenges	5	
P8	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	5	4	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, Interviews, Survey, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Cognitive ergonomics, Storyboard	Figma, Miro, FireBase, Adobe suite	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Extracting user information, hiring UX professionals, acquiring a large volume of users for meaningful testing.	4	
P9	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	3	1	User flow map, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, Wireframing, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Cognitive ergonomics, Storyboard	Cannot answer	Iterations with user feedback, Responsive design for different devices	Has no challenges	5	

P10	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	5	1	1	High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Competitive analysis, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard	Miro	Iterations with user feedback	Has no challenges	5
P11	Current position is focused on UX work	4	3	3	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Cognitive ergonomics, Storyboard	Figma, Xd	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Extract user information, Lack of UX knowledge, Understand the target audience	3
P12	Does not know what UX or UX techniques are	1	1	1	Cannot answer	Cannot answer	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Cannot answer	3
P13	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	5	3	3	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Interviews, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Storyboard	Google Analytics	A/B testing	Extract user information, Understand the target audience	4
P14	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	3	1	1	Does not adopt	Does not use	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, User-centered development	Validating the game with the end user, Lack of UX knowledge, Understanding the target audience, Hiring UX professionals	5
P15	Current position is focused on UX work	2	3	3	High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Interviews, Wireframing, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture	Figma, Miro, Google Analytics	Iterations with user feedback	Game validation with the end user	5
P16	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	4	4	3	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Cognitive ergonomics	Miro	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, data analysis and telemetry, user-centered development.	Game validation with the end user, Understanding the target audience, Applications of UX techniques	4
P17	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	2	1	High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Competitive analysis, Survey, Wireframing, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Cognitive ergonomics	Wireframing, Miro, Google Analytics	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing	Lack of UX knowledge, Applications of UX techniques, Hiring UX professionals	5
P18	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	5	1	3	High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Wireframing, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Analytics	Miro, FireBase	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, data analysis and telemetry, user-centered development.	Understand the target audience	5
P19	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	3	1	1	GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Does not use	A/B testing, Responsive design for different devices	Game validation with the end user, Extract user information	4
P20	Current position is focused on UX work	5	5	4	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Wireframe	Figma, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Game validation with end users, Hiring UX professionals	5

P21	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	5	4	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Interviews, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Miro, lucidchart	Iterations with user feedback	Extract user information, Understand the target audience	5
P22	Current position is focused on UX work	5	5	3	User flow map, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Competitive analysis, Interviews, Survey, Wireframing, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Cognitive ergonomics, Storyboard	proprietary tools	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Has no challenges	5
P23	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	3	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Wireframe, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Figma, Miro	Responsive design for different devices	Hiring UX professionals	4
P24	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	5	1	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, Interviews, Survey, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard	Miro	Iterations with user feedback, Data analysis and telemetry, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Has no challenges	5
P25	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	4	1	1	High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Competitive analysis, Interviews, Survey, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document)	Figma, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Lack of UX knowledge, Understand the target audience	5
P26	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	5	4	4	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Wireframe, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Invision, Wireframing	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Game validation with the end user, Extract user information	5
P27	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	5	1	1	Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Interviews, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Understand the target audience, Hiring UX professionals	5
P28	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	5	3	1	Cannot answer	Cannot answer	Iterations with user feedback	Cannot answer	5
P29	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	1	1	High-fidelity prototype, Teste de usabilidade, Storyboard	Paper prototyping	Iterations with user feedback	Game validation with the end user, Extract user information	4
P30	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	3	1	1	GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Cannot answer	A/B testing, Responsive design for different devices	There are no challenges, I don't know the answer.	5

P31	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	3	1	1	GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document), Does not adopt	Does not use	Does not adopt	Lack of UX knowledge, Cannot answer	4
P32	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	4	2	High-fidelity prototype, Personas, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document), Storyboard	Google Analytics, Does not use, Steam Analytics	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development	Lack of UX knowledge, Hiring UX professionals, Cannot answer	5
P33	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	4	1	1	Does not adopt	Does not use	Iterations with user feedback	Lack of UX knowledge, Applications of UX techniques, Hiring UX professionals	5
P34	Current position is focused on UX work	5	3	3	User flow map, Wireframe, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document), Storyboard	Wireframing	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Game validation with the end user, Applications of UX techniques	5
P35	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	5	5	3	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Personas, Competitive analysis, Interviews, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Storyboard	Figma, Google Analytics	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, User-centered development	Game validation with the end user, Extracting user information, Understanding the target audience, Applications of UX techniques	5
P36	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	3	1	1	Benchmarking, Competitive analysis, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document)	Testing within the engines themselves, following the scope designed in Clip Studio.	Does not adopt	Lack of UX knowledge, Applications of UX techniques, Hiring UX professionals	3
P37	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	3	3	1	User flow map, Usability testing, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Storyboard	Wireframing, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, Focus group testing	Has no challenges	5
P38	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	1	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Interviews, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Cognitive ergonomics	Google Analytics, FireBase	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, data analysis and telemetry.	Has no challenges	5
P39	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	5	3	4	Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, Interviews, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Cognitive ergonomics, Storyboard	Figma, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Validating the game with the end user, Extracting user information, Hiring UX professionals	5
P40	Current position is focused on UX work	5	4	2	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Survey, Wireframe, Cognitive ergonomics, Storyboard	Does not use	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Extracting user information, Hiring UX professionals	5
P41	Current position is focused on UX work	5	1	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Personas, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Figma, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	The biggest challenge for indie game studios is securing investment, making it difficult to hire a UX specialist, in addition to designers, to fit within the budget.	5

P42	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	3	1	User flow map, Usability testing, Interviews, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard	Wireframing, Google Analytics	A/B testing, Data analysis and telemetry, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Understand the target audience	5
P43	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	3	3	2	Usability testing, Interviews, Storyboard	Miro	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, User-centered development	Game validation with the end user, Extract user information	4
P44	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	2	2	2	Cannot answer	Google Analytics	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, data analysis and telemetry.	Has no challenges	3
P45	Current position is focused on UX work	5	5	5	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Personas, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Cognitive ergonomics	Figma	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices, Authorial model for target audience analysis (Player typology)	Game validation with the end user, Extract user information	4
P46	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	5	3	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Competitive analysis, Interviews, Survey, Cognitive ergonomics, Storyboard	Google Analytics, steam	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, data analysis and telemetry, user-centered development.	Validating the game with the end user, Extracting user information, Lack of UX knowledge, Understanding the target audience, Applying UX techniques, Hiring UX professionals	5
P47	Current position is focused on UX work	5	5	5	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Interviews, Survey, Wireframe, Storyboard	Figma, Google Analytics	A/B testing, User-centered development	Extract user information, Understand the target audience	5
P48	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	1	1	1	Does not adopt	Does not use	Iterations with user feedback	Cannot answer	5
P49	Current position is focused on UX work	5	5	3	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Wireframe, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Miro, Google Analytics	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Extract user information, Applications of UX techniques	5
P50	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	4	3	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Wireframe, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Figma, Google Analytics	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, data analysis and telemetry.	Game validation with the end user, Extract user information, Understand the target audience	4
P51	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	2	1	1	High-fidelity prototype, wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document)	Figma	Iterations with user feedback, Responsive design for different devices	Validating the game with the end user, Extracting user information, Understanding the target audience, Hiring UX professionals	5

P52	Current position is focused on UX work	2	2	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Wireframe, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Figma, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, Does not adopt	Extract user information, Understand the target audience, Hiring UX professionals	5
P53	Current position is focused on UX work	5	5	5	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture	Figma, Wireframing	A/B testing, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Validating the game with the end user, Extracting user information, Understanding the target audience, Applying UX techniques, Hiring UX professionals	5
P54	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	3	3	1	User flow map, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Cognitive ergonomics, Storyboard	Figma	Iterations with user feedback	Game validation with the end user	4
P55	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	4	3	1	Usability testing, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Miro	A/B testing	Game validation with the end user, Lack of UX knowledge	5
P56	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	2	1	1	Does not adopt	Figma	Iterations with user feedback	Extract user information, Understand the target audience, Hiring UX professionals	5
P57	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	5	3	1	High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Wireframing, Miro	A/B testing, User-centered development	Game validation with the end user	4
P58	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	3	1	1	User flow map, Competitive analysis, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Miro	User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Game validation with the end user, Extract user information	5
P59	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	4	2	1	High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Interviews	Figma, FireBase	Iterations with user feedback	Game validation with the end user, Extracting user information, Lack of UX knowledge, Applications of UX techniques	5
P60	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	4	3	2	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype	Figma, Miro, FireBase	A/B testing, Responsive design for different devices	Game validation with the end user, Understand the target audience	4
P61	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	4	3	2	User flow map, Usability testing, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Figma	Responsive design for different devices	Game validation with the end user	4

P62	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	4	3	3	GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Miro	Cannot answer	Understanding the target audience, Applications of UX techniques	5
P63	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	3	1	Cannot answer,	Figma	Iterations with user feedback	Game validation with the end user	4
P64	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	1	1	Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document)	Figma, Miro	A/B testing	Extract user information, Lack of UX knowledge	4
P65	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	3	3	1	User flow map, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Interviews, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document)	Figma, Miro, FireBase	A/B testing, data analysis and telemetry	Game validation with the end user, Application of UX techniques, Hiring UX professionals	5
P66	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	5	5	3	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, Interviews, Survey, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture	Figma, Miro, Google Analytics, FireBase	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, data analysis and telemetry, user-centered development, responsive design for different devices.	Cannot answer	5
P67	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	5	3	1	User flow map, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Interviews, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Miro, Google Analytics	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing	Extract user information, Lack of UX knowledge, Applications of UX techniques	5
P68	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	5	5	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, Interviews, Survey, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Cognitive ergonomics, Storyboard	Figma, Wireframing, Miro, Google Analytics	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, data analysis and telemetry, user-centered development, responsive design for different devices.	Game validation with the end user, Understand the target audience	5
P69	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	4	4	3	Benchmarking	Figma, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing	Game validation with the end user	4
P70	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	2	3	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Personas, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document), User flow	Figma, Miro, Trello	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, User-centered development	Extract user information, Lack of UX knowledge, Applications of UX techniques	5
P71	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	5	3	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Personas, Competitive analysis, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Storyboard	Figma, Wireframing, Google Analytics, FireBase	Iterations with user feedback, Data analysis and telemetry, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Understand the target audience, Hiring UX professionals	5

P72	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	3	1	1	High-fidelity prototype, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document), Storyboard	Miro	Cannot answer	Validating the game with the end user, Lack of UX knowledge, Applications of UX techniques, Hiring UX professionals	5
P73	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	5	3	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, Interviews, Survey, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Cognitive ergonomics, Storyboard	Figma, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Game validation with the end user, Understand the target audience	5
P74	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	5	3	2	High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Wireframe, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document), Storyboard	Figma	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Game validation with end users, Hiring UX professionals	5
P75	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	3	3	1	User flow map, Competitive analysis, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Wireframing, Miro	Iterations with user feedback	Understand the target audience	5
P76	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	3	2	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Figma, Miro, Google Analytics	Cannot answer	Lack of UX knowledge, Understanding the target audience, Cannot answer	4
P77	Current position is focused on UX work	5	3	2	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, Interviews, Survey, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Cognitive ergonomics, Storyboard	Figma, Wireframing, Miro, Google Analytics	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Validating the game with the end user, Extracting user information, Lack of UX knowledge, Hiring UX professionals, Investing in UX	5
P78	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	4	2	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Personas, Competitive analysis, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Extracting user information, Hiring UX professionals	5
P79	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	3	4	User flow map, Usability testing	Does not use	Iterations with user feedback, Responsive design for different devices	Cannot answer	5
P80	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	3	1	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Benchmarking, Personas, Interviews, Survey, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Game validation with the end user, Application of UX techniques, Hiring UX professionals	4
P81	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	4	1	1	User flow map, Survey, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Miro	A/B testing, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Extract user information, Lack of UX knowledge	5

P82	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	5	5	5	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, Interviews, Survey, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Cognitive ergonomics, Storyboard	Figma, Invision, Wireframing, Miro, Google Analytics, Firebase, Proprietary Software (EA, Ubisoft, Warner, etc.)	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, data analysis and telemetry, user-centered development, responsive design for different devices.	Hiring UX professionals	5
P83	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	3	2	User flow map, Wireframe, Information architecture	Figma, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, User-centered development	Hiring UX professionals	4
P84	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	1	1	1	Does not adopt	Does not use	Iterations with user feedback	Cannot answer	5
P85	Current position is focused on UX work	1	1	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Wireframe, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Figma	User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Hiring UX professionals	5
P86	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	5	5	5	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, Interviews, Survey, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Cognitive ergonomics, Storyboard. We have a UX partner company.	We have a UX Partner Company.	We have a UX Partner Company.	There are no challenges. We have a UX Partner Company.	5
P87	Current position is focused on UX work	5	5	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, Interviews, Survey, Wireframe, Information architecture, Storyboard	Figma, Google Analytics, FireBase	A/B testing, User-centered development	Game validation with the end user, Extract user information, Understand the target audience	5
P88	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	3	1	1	Usability testing, Personas, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document)	Figma, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Game validation with the end user, Lack of UX knowledge, Hiring UX professionals	5
P89	Current position is focused on UX work	5	5	3	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, Interviews, Survey, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Cognitive ergonomics, Storyboard	Figma, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Has no challenges	5
P90	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	3	2	1	Usability testing, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document), Storyboard	Figma	Iterations with user feedback	Lack of UX knowledge, Applications of UX techniques, Hiring UX professionals	5
P91	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	3	1	1	High-fidelity prototype, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document), Storyboard	Does not use	Does not adopt	Cannot answer	5

P92	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	5	4	4	User flow map, Usability testing, Interviews, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Cognitive ergonomics	Figma, Wireframing, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Extracting user information, Lack of UX knowledge, Understanding the target audience, Applications of UX techniques, Hiring UX professionals	4
P93	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	3	1	1	User flow map, Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard	Miro, Google Analytics	Iterations with user feedback, Responsive design for different devices	Game validation with the end user, Extract user information	5
P94	Current position is focused on UX work	4	5	2	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Benchmarking, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Miro	Cannot answer	Cannot answer	5
P95	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	5	1	2	Usability testing, Benchmarking, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Does not use	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development	Cannot answer	5
P96	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	4	2	1	Usability testing, Personas, Competitive analysis, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Lack of UX knowledge, Applications of UX techniques	5
P97	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	3	1	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Wireframe, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Figma, Miro	Responsive design for different devices	Cannot answer	5
P98	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	5	5	4	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Storyboard	Figma, Wireframing, Google Analytics, FireBase	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, data analysis and telemetry, user-centered development, responsive design for different devices.	Has no challenges	5
P99	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	4	1	2	User flow map, Usability testing, Personas, Survey, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Invision	Iterations with user feedback, Responsive design for different devices	Extracting user information, Lack of UX knowledge, Applications of UX techniques, Hiring UX professionals	5
P100	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	5	3	2	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Benchmarking, Personas, Competitive analysis, Interviews, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development	Extracting user information, Lack of UX knowledge, Hiring UX professionals	5
P101	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	5	2	1	Interviews	Does not use	Iterations with user feedback	Applications of UX techniques	4
P102	Current position is focused on UX work	5	4	2	User flow map, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Storyboard	Figma	A/B testing	Extract user information	5

P103	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	3	1	1	Benchmarking, Interviews, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document)	Miro	Iterations with user feedback	Extract user information	5
P104	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	5	3	2	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Interviews, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard,	Figma, Miro, Google Analytics,	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices.	Extracting user information, Hiring UX professionals	5
P105	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	4	2	1	Personas, Competitive analysis, Storyboard	Miro	Iterations with user feedback	Game validation with the end user, Extract user information	4
P106	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	5	4	2	High-fidelity prototype, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Cognitive ergonomics	Miro, Google Analytics	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Game validation with the end user, Extract user information	5
P107	Does not know what UX or UX techniques are	3	1	1	Cannot answer	Miro	Cannot answer	Cannot answer	4
P108	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	4	3	2	High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Competitive analysis, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard	Cannot answer	Iterations with user feedback	Lack of UX knowledge, Applications of UX techniques, Hiring UX professionals	4
P109	Current position is focused on UX work	5	3	3	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Interviews, Survey, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture	Figma, Miro	Does not develop games.	Does not develop games.	5
P110	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	3	2	1	Cannot answer	Figma, Cannot answer	Cannot answer	Cannot answer	4
P111	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	5	5	5	User flow map, Interviews, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Cognitive ergonomics	Figma, Miro, Google Analytics, FireBase	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Cannot answer	4
P112	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	3	2	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Interviews, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document)	Figma, Miro, Google Analytics	Data analysis and telemetry	Game validation with the end user	5

P113	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	4	2	2	Usability testing, Benchmarking, Competitive analysis, Interviews, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document)	Does not use	Data analysis and telemetry	Validating the game with the end user, Extracting user information, Lack of UX knowledge, Understanding the target audience, Applying UX techniques, Hiring UX professionals	5
P114	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	5	4	3	Usability testing, Benchmarking, Personas, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Information architecture, Cognitive ergonomics, Storyboard	Figma	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development	Game validation with the end user, Lack of UX knowledge, Hiring UX professionals	5
P115	Current position is focused on UX work	3	2	1	User flow map, Benchmarking, Wireframe, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Figma, Miro, Google Analytics, FireBase	A/B testing, Data analysis and telemetry, Responsive design for different devices	Lack of UX knowledge, Hiring UX professionals	4
P116	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	2	1	High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Competitive analysis	Figma	Iterations with user feedback, Responsive design for different devices	Game validation with the end user, Extrair informações do usuário	4
P117	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	5	1	1	Cannot answer	Cannot answer	Cannot answer	Cannot answer	5
P118	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	3	1	1	GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document), Cannot answer	Cannot answer	Cannot answer	Cannot answer	5
P119	Current position is focused on UX work	4	5	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Wireframe, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Wireframing, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, responsive design for different devices.	Extract user information	4
P120	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	4	2	1	Usability testing, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document)	Figma	Iterations with user feedback, Responsive design for different devices	Extracting user information, Applications of UX techniques, Hiring UX professionals	4
P121	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	4	3	Interviews, I think that question is wrong, would it be the selection process?	Figma, Miro	A/B testing	Understanding the target audience, Applications of UX techniques, Hiring UX professionals	5
P122	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	4	2	3	High-fidelity prototype, Competitive analysis, Interviews, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document)	Figma, Miro	Iterations with user feedback	Validating the game with the end user, Extracting user information, Lack of UX knowledge, Understanding the target audience, Hiring UX professionals	5

P123	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	4	2	4	High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Personas, GDD/GAD (Game Design/Art Document), Storyboard	Figma	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Game validation with the end user, Extracting user information, Lack of UX knowledge, Understanding the target audience	5
P124	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	5	3	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Interviews, Survey, Storyboard	Figma, Miro, Google Analytics	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, data analysis and telemetry, responsive design for different devices.	Validating the game with the end user, Extracting user information, Hiring UX professionals	5
P125	Has worked with UX in the industry at some point	4	2	1	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Personas, Competitive analysis, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Wireframing, Miro, Google Analytics	Iterations with user feedback, Data analysis and telemetry, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices	Understand the target audience, Hiring UX professionals	5
P126	Has heard of UX in lectures, college, or courses, but has never worked with it	4	1	1	High-fidelity prototype, Interviews	Google Analytics	Iterations with user feedback, User-centered development	Lack of UX knowledge, Applications of UX techniques	5
P127	Current position is focused on UX work	5	4	3	User flow map, High-fidelity prototype, Usability testing, Personas, Competitive analysis, Wireframe, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Miro, Google Analytics	Iterations with user feedback, A/B testing, User-centered development, Responsive design for different devices, Conducting playtest events with users.	Game validation with the end user, Extract user information	5
P128	Has heard of UX and has already applied some UX techniques	4	1	1	User flow map, Benchmarking, Competitive analysis, GDD (Game Design Document) or GAD (Game Art Document), Storyboard	Figma, Miro	Iterations with user feedback, Responsive design for different devices	Game validation with the end user, Understand the target audience	5